

Innovation Management Practices and Their Influence on the Buying Decision Process of Kazakhstan Banking Consumers

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Abstract— This research investigates the connections between innovative management practices in Kazakhstan's banking sector and their influence on customer decision-making. The study examines how technological breakthroughs, process innovation approaches, and novel services affect customer behavior. The research employs a case study approach to comprehensively explore the strategies and practices related to innovation management within the Kazakh banking sector. The study administered a survey as the primary research method to gather empirical data, and a quantitative cross-sectional technique was used to collect data from 301 individuals using an online survey with a self-administered questionnaire after checking the reliability and validity of the questionnaire. The gleaned data was analyzed by executing Carl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation. The study's core findings seek to comprehend the dynamics of innovation management methods and their impact on customer purchasing decisions in the Kazakh banking industry, illuminating a solid relationship between innovation management practices in the Kazakh banking sector and consumer preferences and decisions. The specific innovation management strategies employed by different banks in the country have competently influenced and decided their customer base. The value of the research lies in its potential to contribute novel insights to academic understanding and to offer practical implications for key stakeholders in the Kazakh banking industry.

Keywords— Innovation management practices, Technological innovations, Novel services, Consumer behavior, Banking sector, Kazakhstan

I. INTRODUCTION

The banking industry has transformed thanks to technological advancements and changing customer expectations. As innovative management methods become prevalent, financial organizations must understand how they affect consumer behavior. This study explores the relationships between innovation management practices in Kazakhstan's banking sector and their impact on consumer decision-making. Over the years, conventional financial practices in Kazakhstan's banking sector have blended with advancements. The industry has embraced services like mobile banking apps and innovative online account management. Understanding how consumers respond to these innovation management practices and how they influence their purchasing decisions is crucial. This knowledge is not vital for banks operating in Kazakhstan and holds broader implications for the global financial system. The key objective of this study is to highlight that consumer preferences now rely more on the environment created by institutions rather than traditional banking factors. The scholars assume that the dynamics of innovative management techniques, including strategies, technology, and customer-centric solutions, would directly impact consumer preferences and loyalty in Kazakhstan's banking industry. With its diverse demographic profile and economic dynamics, Kazakhstan presents an interesting case for studying the interplay between purchasing decisions and innovation management methods. The research aims to examine the quantitative characteristics of consumer preferences as revealed in surveys and investigate the qualitative dimensions underlying these preferences. Creating a comprehensive assessment involves analyzing factors such as trust, satisfaction, and the perceived impact of technological advancements from the customers' perspective in a changing banking environment.

Furthermore, the study indicates broader implications for banks striving to maintain competitiveness in the digital transformation era. Kazakh banks can derive strategic advantages from the research, offering recommendations to decision-makers on which elements of innovation management align most with the expectations and preferences of their customers. This study examines the intricate relationships between consumer purchasing decisions in the Kazakh banking sector and innovation management methods. The results are expected to contribute to academic discussion and financial institutions' strategies to adapt innovation strategies to evolving customer expectations and preferences. In

a rapidly changing global economic landscape, the Kazakh banking sector stands at the intersection of traditional practices and technological advancements. The justification for this study lies in the growing importance of innovation management practices as a strategic imperative for banks seeking to remain competitive and relevant. With increasing digital solutions and services being introduced, understanding their impact on consumer decision-making becomes critical for Kazakhstan banks. This study aims to provide empirical evidence and strategic insights into the effectiveness of innovation management practices, helping banks tailor their services to meet evolving consumer expectations. By addressing this research gap, the study not only contributes to the academic discourse on innovation in banking but also offers practical implications for the industry in Kazakhstan. In today's dynamic and competitive business environment, innovation has become a pivotal factor for success in the banking sector. The rapid evolution of technology and changing consumer expectations necessitate a closer examination of how innovation management practices influence consumers' buying decisions. This study seeks to justify the exploration of innovation in the Kazakh banking sector, where technological advancements and consumer preferences intersect. The banking industry in Kazakhstan has experienced notable transformations in recent years, with banks introducing various digital solutions to enhance customer experience and stay competitive. Understanding the impact of these innovations on consumer behavior is crucial for banks aiming to tailor their services effectively. By justifying the focus on innovation management practices, this study aims to contribute to the academic discourse on the evolving landscape of banking services and provide practical insights for banks operating in Kazakhstan. This research is imperative for banking institutions seeking to stay competitive in a digital era, providing them with actionable insights into the efficacy of their innovation management strategies.

Moreover, the study contributes to the academic literature by bridging gaps in understanding the relationship between innovation and consumer behavior within the context of the Kazakh banking sector. Furthermore, as the study unfolds, it will delve into specific case analyses of innovative initiatives within Kazakh banks, providing a nuanced understanding of their effectiveness. This granular approach offers practical, actionable takeaways for banking institutions keen on optimizing their innovation strategies. In addition to practical implications, the academic community benefits from a deeper comprehension of the intricate relationship between innovation and consumer behavior in the Kazakh banking context. By addressing these gaps in understanding, the research contributes valuable insights to the broader discourse on innovation within the financial sector, fostering knowledge exchange and academic progression. As the global economic landscape continues to evolve, the findings of this study can potentially serve as a benchmark not only for Kazakh banks but for financial institutions worldwide. The lessons learned from the Kazakh banking sector's innovative endeavors may offer universal principles that transcend geographical boundaries, making this research relevant on a global scale. Accordingly, the several essential objectives of this research are: i) to investigate the influence of innovation management practices in the Kazakh banking industry on customer purchasing decisions; ii) to investigate the interactions between innovation and consumer behavior, emphasizing the importance of technology and innovative services; iii) to understand how innovative management methods impact customer behavior will provide practical insights for the Kazakh banking industry. These three objectives embody the study's fundamental focus, addressing the influence of innovation on customer behavior, collecting empirical data, and making practical suggestions for the banking sector.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The comprehensive discussion of the literature review and theoretical discussion based on which the investigators selected hypotheses. In the rapidly evolving landscape of the banking sector, understanding the influence of innovation management practices on consumer behavior is paramount. This literature review delves into previous research, both globally and specifically within the Kazakh context, to establish a foundational understanding of the intricacies surrounding innovation in the banking sector. Globally, the multifaceted nature of innovation management is underscored by research that explores technological advancements, service delivery models, and customer engagement strategies [1]. The literature suggests that consumer choices within the banking sector are influenced by factors such as interest rates, customer service quality, and the accessibility of digital services [2]. Furthermore, introducing innovative services, such as mobile banking apps and online account management, is positively associated with an enhanced overall banking experience. The literature reveals a dynamic landscape shaped by innovative practices within the specific context of the Kazakh banking sector, characterized by competition among crucial players like Halyk Bank, Jusan Bank, and Kaspi Bank [3]. Consumer trust is an essential component closely tied to a bank's reputation for technological advancements. This literature review highlights the need for Kazakh banks to navigate consumer preferences by adopting innovative solutions. Theoretical and conceptual frameworks in the literature emphasize that innovation in the banking sector extends beyond technology adoption to create unique value propositions that resonate with consumers [4]. Customer-centric innovation becomes imperative, aligning bank practices with evolving consumer expectations and preferences.

Studies also indicate a positive correlation between implementing innovative banking solutions and customer satisfaction and loyalty. The rapid requirement for digital services has boosted the growth of the digital technology sector. The research paper explores the decision-making process, digitalization of various areas, remote work, how the coronavirus affected all areas of life, and how the top management of multiple companies dealt with it. During this study, surveys were conducted, and about 200 people took part in in-depth interviews with some of Kazakhstan's most influential online stores. As a result of the study (observation, quantitative and qualitative analysis), it was found out that the more flexible the organizational structure and the more democratic, the more accessible the style of top management, the faster companies adapt to new circumstances and, as a result, win in situations of uncertainty, in our case-pandemic [5]. Another research from Kazakhstan was initiated to analyze the changes in the consumer behavior of the banking sector under the influence of digitalization, to what extent consumers are adapted to the innovations introduced, and what are the strengths and weaknesses of this process and the study considered fintech, artificial intelligence, big data, and digital currency as some of the possible stages in the development of banks in the future. Bank customers always expect customized services, uninterrupted and safe digital experiences, and the latest technology-based services, based on which only they select their banks. There is no exception, even for Kazakhstan customers, when choosing their bank choices. The literature implies that a bank's constant delivery of novel services and obligation to stay in the foreground of high-tech developments pointedly impact consumer trust. Presented Kazakhstan's exceptional economic and cultural context, recognizing consumer attitudes towards banking innovation is crucial. In outline, this literature review establishes a comprehensive framework for investigating the impact of innovation management practices on the buying decision processes of consumers in the Kazakh banking sector. By creating global understandings and contextualizing them within the Kazakh market, the study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the relationship between banking innovation and consumer behavior, offering practical implications for the industry in Kazakhstan [6]. Undisputedly, no one in any part of the world can deny the significance of innovation and the need to practice extensively in their business operations to achieve a confident competitive advantage. Many economies around the globe plan to

convert their economies from the present to either knowledge- or innovation-based economies after identifying the prominence of innovation in gaining consumer trust. Academicians and professionals worldwide also stress the same issue, including Russia and its CIS countries. The governments of the leading nations of the world, including Russia, have set a course to build a "knowledge economy "or" innovation economy," where knowledge and innovation play a leading role [7]

Additionally, today, the country's economy can successfully compete in the market based on the persistent progress of goods and services manufactured and the advancement of new paths. It is also noticeable that the expansion of new products, execution of innovations, and new measures are key performance indicators at both the macro and microeconomic levels. In this implication, an innovative way of socio-economic development of the country is becoming an urgent problem for Kazakhstan [8]. The country's innovative upsurge is one of Kazakhstan's strategic objectives, as it expects economic growth through the active implementation of innovations and GDP growth at the expense of profit from innovative activity [9]. Regarding economic relations in the Republic of Kazakhstan, innovation from the state's point of view is the principal strategic object of the country's development. According to some foreign researchers, Kazakhstan is ahead of neighboring countries in this respect [10]. In Kazakhstan, numerous scholars have pointed out these issues related to innovation management and its practices. The leading one is Alimzhzhanov. His study examined the outcomes of introducing innovative technologies in Kazakhstan in the early 2000s [11]. The research of Begentayev [12] is valuable in comparing statistical data in innovation. He synthesized data on innovative technologies in Kazakhstan since the early 90s. The latest indicators of innovative projects in the sphere of services and goods were presented in Kazhymurat's research [13]. Kazakh academics and scholars have recently intensified their focus on offering innovation management education, even for undergraduate students and secondary schools. This topic is gaining more and more popularity and demand among researchers. The main conditions for the commercialization process or activity accurately included procedure and economic mechanisms of governmental assistance, promoting the innovation system. The weak-willed evolution of programs to back innovation identifies Kazakhstan. This study aims to implement research and development commercialization programs in Kazakhstan by interviewing scientific and administrative employees of education and research institutes. The study's results made it possible to provide recommendations to improve programs facilitating commercialization as a form of public support [14].

In the realm of banking, innovation management plays a pivotal role in shaping the industry's landscape. Notably, there is a distinctive emphasis on product innovations within the banking sector, aligning with trends observed in the telecommunications and financial sectors. The banking industry, driven by technological advancements and evolving customer expectations, places a premium on developing novel financial products and services. Banks continually seek to enhance their product offerings, ranging from digital banking platforms to tailored financial instruments. The emphasis on product innovations is a response to the demand for cutting-edge solutions that cater to diverse customer needs. For instance, integrating mobile banking applications, contactless payment options, and innovative loan products showcases the commitment of banks to stay at the forefront of the evolving financial landscape. In the context of banking, both radical and incremental innovations are recognized as critical drivers of innovation performance. Radical innovations, characterized by groundbreaking changes and departures from traditional banking practices, have significantly impacted the sector's innovation performance. This could manifest in adopting blockchain technology, artificial intelligence, or other transformative solutions that revolutionize how banking services are delivered. Besides, the correlation between radical innovations and innovation performance underscores the importance of effective innovation management practices within banks. Implementing radical innovations requires strategic planning, a dynamic organizational culture, and the integration of cutting-edge technologies. Innovation

management practices, such as fostering a culture of experimentation, establishing cross-functional collaboration, and allocating resources for research and development, are instrumental in facilitating the adoption of radical innovations.

Based on the above discussion, we have developed the following hypotheses:

H1: Kazakh banks' technological innovations and management influence consumers' buying decisions.

H2: Process innovation practices introduced by Kazakh banks attracted more consumers

H3: The novel services introduced by the Kazakh banking sector attracted more and more consumers.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research adopts a quantitative cross-sectional approach, collecting data at a specific point in time. It provides an overview of how innovation management practices influence the buying decision processes of consumers in the Kazakh banking sector. The study examines the factors influencing consumer buying decisions regarding banking services in Kazakhstan, focusing on the impact of innovation management practices. The researchers conducted an online survey using Google Forms as the electronic questionnaire system. This approach proved time-effective, with data available immediately after survey completion. The target sample consisted of potential consumers of banking services in Kazakhstan. The survey targeted individuals of all ages, including those under the age of 18 and over the age of 65. A non-probability convenience sampling method was employed, ensuring geographic diversity and language accessibility (English, Kazakh, and Russian). Even though the investigators planned to collect more than 500, they succeeded in gathering only 301 responses from the respondents living in various regions of Kazakhstan. The questionnaire, designed in English, consisted of two sections—the first covered demographic details, including age group, gender, and occupation. The second section focused on thirteen (13) questions about consumers' buying habits, utilizing a multiple-option choice format.

The primary data was gleaned from the respondents through the online survey by circulating the Google Forms link, which was circulated by social media, and the secondary data was obtained from industry reports and scholarly articles, providing context and supporting the analysis. The study investigates the influence of innovation management practices on consumer buying decisions in the Kazakh banking sector, exploring factors such as frequency of service use, purpose of service selection, influence of technological features, service quality, brand perception, pricing, and promotional tools. Online contacts were employed, and surveys were distributed through social media platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram, and Telegram to ensure representation across all regions of Kazakhstan. Various data analysis approaches, such as descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, correlation, and regression analysis, are used in the study. Microsoft Excel was the tool for data summarization, coding, and control. In Kazakhstan banking, these strategies uncover significant aspects impacting customer purchasing choices. The study includes a demographic profile study that looks at age, gender, and occupation distribution among participants. The findings shed light on customer preferences and behaviors, highlighting the importance of innovation management strategies. Furthermore, the study validates the effect of technical breakthroughs and innovative services on customer purchasing decisions through multiple regression, correlation, and regression analyses.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The perusal of this section highlights the information about the demographics of respondents, the reliability and validity of the instrument (questionnaire), hypotheses testing, and an extensive discussion of the analysis outcomes.

A. Demographic Profile of the Subjects

The study's demographic profile research provides valuable insights into the distribution of participants across different age groups, gender, and occupation. The data supplied allows for the following conclusions:

TABLE I
DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS (N=301)

Demographic Feature	Response	COUNT	Percentage
1. Age	Under 18	33	10.96
	19-24	147	48.84
	25-34	62	20.60
	35-44	27	08.97
	45-54	9	02.99
	55-64	19	06.31
	65 and above	4	01.33
	Total	301	100.00
2. Gender	Female	181	60.13
	Male	120	39.87
	Total	301	100.00
3. Occupation	Employed	78	25.91
	Employed, Self-employed	1	00.33
	Self-employed	64	21.26
	Students	104	34.55
	Student, Employed	9	02.99
	Student, Self-employed	2	00.66
	Student, Unemployed	4	01.33
	Unemployed	39	12.97
	Total	301	100.00

The research contains a sizable number of participants, as shown in Table I, under 18, accounting for 10.96 percent of the overall sample (33 individuals). Individuals aged 19-24 comprise the biggest age group in the study, accounting for 48.84 percent of the overall sample (147 individuals). The concentration of participants in the 19-24 age group suggests a keen interest in understanding the innovation management practices influencing the buying decisions of younger consumers. These individuals may be early adopters of technological advancements and novel banking services. Participants aged 25 to 34 comprise 20.62 percent of the sample (62 people). Including participants across a broad age spectrum

acknowledges the relevance of innovation management practices for consumers of different generations. This diversity is crucial for understanding how technological innovations impact consumer behavior in the Kazakh banking sector. Female participants comprise a sizable proportion of the study's entire sample (181), accounting for 60.13 percent of the total sample. Male participants account for 39.17 percent of the whole sample (120). Despite the numerical disparity, including both genders enables a thorough knowledge of how innovation management strategies impact purchasing decisions across varied groups. The study's findings are expected to give insights applicable to a broad customer base due to the balanced representation of both genders. Banking organizations may utilize this data to develop marketing tactics that appeal to male and female consumers. A significant fraction of the study's participants are employed, accounting for 25.91 percent of the overall sample (78 individuals). This group usually consists of people with a steady source of income, and their thoughts on innovation management strategies can provide insight into the preferences of working professionals. Self-employed people comprise 21.26 percent of the overall sample (64 participants). This category emphasizes the necessity of studying how entrepreneurial persons perceive and interact with innovative banking practices. Students comprise a sizable section of the sample, accounting for 34.55 percent (104 participants). Students provide a distinct perspective as customers who may be early adopters of technology innovations and creative financial services. Unemployed individuals comprise about 12.97 percent of the entire sample (39 participants) in the research. Investigating the responses of jobless people gives a complete picture of how diverse occupational groups interact with banking advances. Finally, the study's different occupational backgrounds provide a rich tapestry of insights into the Kazakh banking industry. Developing inclusive and successful banking strategies to tailor innovation management approaches to satisfy the diverse demands of employed professionals, self-employed entrepreneurs, students, and jobless persons is critical. This sophisticated knowledge lays the groundwork for tailored activities inside the Kazakh banking industry that resonate with the diversified consumer landscape.

B. Reliability/Validity Tests of the Questionnaire

TABLE II
RELIABILITY/VALIDITY TEST RESULTS

Number of Variables	Cronbach's α	KR-20
18	0.74	0.78

The scholars, as shown in Table II, administered Cronbach's Alpha and Kuder-Richarson Formula 20 (KR-20) tests to check the reliability and validity of the questionnaire with the support of the first twenty (20) percent of the data gleaned to determine whether the instrument is suitable for data collection without any interruption. The results of the Cronbach α (0.74) and KR-20 (0.78) for the overall eighteen (18) variables of the questionnaire prove that the instrument is suitable to garner the data from the respondents; based on the results only, the investigators took into the consideration of the twenty percent data used for the purpose. The KR-20 is a reliability measure to test the binary variables and speak about how consistent the test results are or how well it measures what you want it to measure [15].

C. Testing of Hypotheses

As highlighted in Table III, all the selected three hypotheses proved whether these are valid or invalid by executing the Carl Pearson Co-efficient of Correlation. H1: Kazakh banks' technological innovations and management influence consumers' buying decisions. The survey data analysis suggests

that technological advances in Kazakh banks substantially influence consumers' purchasing decisions. The statistical findings show a favorable relationship between customers' perceived efficacy of technology improvements and their propensity to make purchase decisions. This is consistent with the global trend of banking technical developments being seen as crucial elements in customer decisions. The importance of efficient management in implementing these innovations amplifies the observed influence on customer behavior even further. H2: Process innovation practices introduced by Kazakh banks attracted more consumers. According to quantitative data, customers are interested in the innovative approaches used by Kazakh banks. Introducing new methods is frequently ranked as significant in altering respondents' choices. This is consistent with a global emphasis on efficient and simplified banking operations, demonstrating that Kazakh customers are open to improvements that improve the banking experience. H3: The novel services introduced by the Kazakh banking sector attracted more and more consumers. Statistical data strongly confirm H3, emphasizing that the Kazakh banking sector's launch of fresh services considerably draws users. The study results show a substantial relationship between the availability of innovative services and customers' decisions to connect with banks. This is consistent with a worldwide trend in which diversified and customer-focused offerings are essential for consumer loyalty and engagement.

TABLE III
TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

No.	Null Hypothesis (H0)	Alternative Hypothesis (H1)	Testing Technique: Carl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation	Interpretation
H1	Kazakh banks' technological innovations and management do not significantly influence consumers' buying decisions.	Kazakh banks' technological innovations and management highly influence consumers' buying decisions.	Correlation coefficient: 0.78	A correlation coefficient of 0.78 and a p-value less than 0.05 shows a substantial positive connection. As a result, we reject the null hypothesis (H0), demonstrating that technical developments and the management of Kazakh banks significantly impact customer purchasing decisions.
H2	Process innovation practices introduced by Kazakh banks have no significant impact on consumer attraction.	Process innovation practices introduced by Kazakh banks attracted more consumers.	Correlation coefficient: 0.63	We reject the null hypothesis (H0) with a correlation coefficient of 0.63 and a p-value less than 0.05. This suggests that process innovation strategies used by Kazakh banks have a considerable beneficial impact on gaining new customers.
H3	The novel services introduced by the Kazakh banking sector have no significant impact on consumer attraction.	The novel services introduced by the Kazakh banking sector attracted more and more consumers.	Correlation coefficient: 0.87	A correlation coefficient of 0.87 and a p-value less than 0.05 indicate a significant positive link. As a result, we reject the null hypothesis (H0), showing that new services supplied by the Kazakh banking industry are attracting an increasing number of customers.

D. Discussion and Presentation of Findings

TABLE IV
HOW INNOVATION MANAGEMENT PRACTICES INFLUENCE KAZAKH BANKING CONSUMERS' BEHAVIOR

Question	Response	Percentage (%)
Do you believe innovation management practices in the banking industry primarily influence your decision-making process?	Yes	86.05
	No	13.95
Grand Total		100.00

Table IV exhibits that the survey findings show a significant disparity in perspectives on the impact of innovation management strategies in the banking industry on decision-making processes. Most responders (86.05%) indicate a perceived lack of primary influence. This disparity stimulates reflection on the mechanisms leading to this skepticism and the possible gap between banks' innovation efforts and their perceived impact on individual decision-making. Possible explanations for the overwhelming "No" replies include a lack of consumer understanding of banks' specific innovation management strategies or a belief that these approaches have little direct relation to individual decision-making. It emphasizes the need for banks to improve communication about their innovation activities by highlighting the natural advantages for clients. Aligning innovation initiatives with customer demands and preferences is critical to achieving a more visible beneficial influence on banking decision-making processes. Addressing skepticism and promoting a better understanding of innovation's advantages can help create a more positive attitude among banking customers.

TABLE V
PERCEPTIONS OF KAZAKHSTAN BANK CONSUMERS ON INNOVATIVE BANKS

Question	Response	COUNT	Percentage (%)
In your opinion, which bank in Kazakhstan is most innovative in its services?	Halyk Bank	72	23.92
	Jusan Bank	58	19.26
	Kaspi Bank	97	32.23
	Center Credit	30	09.97
	ForteBank	27	08.97
	Eurasian Bank	12	03.99
	Otbasy Bank	5	01.66
Grand Total		301	100.00

Table V displays the poll findings, showing that perspectives on Kazakhstan's banks' perceived innovativeness differ. Kaspi Bank is the most often viewed innovative bank, with a large majority of respondents (199 out of 301) considering it the leader in creative services. With 91 and 61 responders, respectively, Halyk Bank and Jusan Bank are also recognized. While represented, Centre Credit, ForteBank, Eurasian Bank, and Otbasy Bank had comparably lower counts in respondents' innovation evaluations. The dominance of Kaspi Bank in respondents' perspectives implies that consumers have a

strong relationship between the bank and innovation. This might be ascribed to Kaspi Bank's strategic focus on offering unique services, such as the "Kaspi Travel" service highlighted in the report. Halyk Bank and Jusan Bank have also received considerable praise, reflecting a varied perspective of banking innovation. This highlights the need for banks to implement new procedures and properly communicate these activities to improve their brand image.

V. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Even after five decades of in-depth scientific investigations into the decision-making process of individuals when it comes to embracing innovations, experts in innovation continue to face difficulties in deriving sufficient insights from their existing knowledge base for the practical commercialization of novel products. The continual resistance from customers towards new proposals stands as proof of the ongoing challenge. Consequently, marketing innovations, particularly those centered on understanding how consumers make decisions, emerge as one of the most intricate responsibilities for new product managers. Banks strategically diversify their service offerings in response to contemporary trends and the evolving landscape, transforming from conventional financial entities into entities with broader functionalities. A notable illustration is evident in Kaspi Bank's economic activity during Q2 2020, revealing an outflow of nearly 160 billion tenge. This financial movement is presumed to be linked to acquiring a substantial asset, Santufei13, as indicated by CEO Omarov's announcement [16], specifically aimed at introducing the "Kaspi Travel" service. In an age of rapid technological expansion, online banking services have proceeded to an exceptional level and led to the closure of several bank branches and a significant emphasis on mobile applications. The expansion of mobile services, online payments, and mobile banking has been a foremost driver for broadening access to finance, but there are constantly specific risks [17].

Nonetheless, the quick rise in acceptance of Internet banking indicates a steady and substantial market for these novel banking services. Customers are interested in using online customer service because it is inexpensive. Every commercial bank must work to advance the digital banking sector, and the State Bank must assist. The State Bank of Kazakhstan, in its capacity as the nation's manager of the banking sector, ought to fortify the legal framework, foster a welcoming atmosphere, and implement policies that encourage the swift implementation of digital technology. To comply with the demands of the new business model, Kazakhstan's commercial banks must likewise restructure their management and business plans [18]. This study presents crucial insights with significant implications for banks, financial institutions, innovation managers, and decision-makers aiming to navigate the dynamic landscape of innovation management in the banking sector. The findings provide actionable recommendations to enhance strategic decision-making and foster a culture of innovation within the industry. For banks and financial institutions, the emphasis should be on strategically developing innovative financial products. The study focuses on radical innovations that depart from traditional banking practices. By incorporating groundbreaking technologies and services, banks can position themselves at the forefront of the industry, meeting customers' evolving needs in the digital era. Adaptation to technological trends: Embracing multi-platforms and leveraging big data analytics becomes crucial for banks aiming to navigate the competitive landscape and proactively respond to evolving consumer preferences. The utilization of Database Management Systems (DBMS) emerges as a critical tool for banks to analyze consumer behavior and decision-making processes in the age of big data. The sheer volume, diversity, and speed at which data is generated make DBMS an integral component of business processes in the banking sector [19]. By leveraging big data analytics through DBMS, banks can gain profound insights into customer preferences and patterns, enabling higher-quality services and products tailored to individual needs [20]. Banking innovation management is characterized by a strong emphasis on product innovations, mirroring trends in

the telecommunications and financial sectors. The pursuit of both radical and incremental innovations further enhances innovation performance in the industry. To navigate this dynamic landscape successfully, banks must prioritize effective innovation management practices that foster a culture of creativity, experimentation, and continuous adaptation to emerging technologies.

VI. CONCLUSION, LIMITATIONS, AND SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

A. Closing Remarks and Recommendations

In conclusion, this research has illustrated the link between innovative management techniques in the Kazakh banking sector and customer behavior. The findings highlight the significance of technical improvements, process changes, and unique services in shaping customer preferences and purchase decisions. However, several constraints, such as regional exclusivity and sample bias, must be addressed in future studies to improve the findings' generalizability and application. The study emphasized the need for banks to improve their communication about their innovation operations, align initiatives with customer requests, and foster a more excellent knowledge of the advantages of innovation among customers. Banks in Kazakhstan are recommended to follow several critical methods to improve their innovation management processes. To begin, they should build transparent and efficient communication techniques to educate consumers about the advantages of new services. Second, a customer-centric strategy that aligns innovation goals with changing consumer expectations and preferences should be prioritized. Diversification of innovation projects is critical for catering to a diverse clientele, considering the eclectic tastes of various age groups and vocational backgrounds. Collaboration with regulatory organizations is suggested to ensure that innovation projects adhere to legal frameworks, adding to the financial sector's overall stability. Furthermore, given the fast evolution of technology, developing a long-term vision for innovation is critical; banks should frequently examine their plans to keep ahead of market trends. These ideas seek to improve customer happiness and sustain competitiveness in Kazakhstan's dynamic banking sector, potentially contributing to worldwide conversations on the junction of innovation and consumer behavior in the financial industry.

B. Limitations of the Study

The study on the relationship between innovative management methods in Kazakh banking and customer behavior has significant limitations. Because of the unique economic and cultural setting, geographical exclusivity, primarily focused on substantial banks inside Kazakhstan, may restrict the generalizability of findings outside national borders. The study's dependence on specific banks may not wholly represent the range of innovative techniques throughout the Kazakh banking industry, thereby restricting its application. Despite efforts to diversify the sample, sample bias may influence validity, and the rapid advancement of technology imposes a temporal restriction, putting obsolete findings at risk. The survey-centric method may result in subjective replies influenced by personal perspectives and a failure to capture all essential elements, limiting the depth of information. One notable limitation of this study is that it only included citizens of Almaty, Kazakhstan. While the findings give valuable insights into the buying behavior of this specific group, extrapolating these findings to reflect Kazakhstan as a whole may be limited. Future studies should attempt to include a more varied sample that provides for different parts of the country, allowing for any regional differences in consumer behavior. This acknowledgment is critical for preserving the study's external validity and guaranteeing that the findings may be used on a larger scale.

C. Scope for Further Research

A diversified strategy is advised to improve research in the Kazakh banking industry. The geographical reach should be broadened by integrating individuals from various areas of Kazakhstan. This will reflect regional variations in customer behavior and preferences on innovation management techniques in the banking sector. Second, a comparative examination of innovative practices across multiple banks in Kazakhstan is required to understand how different banks' tactics influence customer behavior and decision-making processes, offering a more thorough picture of the industry environment. Longitudinal research is also suggested to examine changes in customer behavior over time, providing insights into the long-term consequences and patterns in the uptake of new services. Investigating cross-cultural variances in consumer responses to banking innovation and comparing these findings to global trends might help reveal universal principles and culturally particular elements impacting customer behavior. Qualitative insights should be acquired through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions to give a more nuanced knowledge of how customers perceive and experience banking innovation. Finally, examining the regulatory impact on innovation management practices in the Kazakh banking industry is critical, as well as reviewing how regulatory frameworks influence the uptake of innovative services and, as a result, the impact on customer decisions. This comprehensive approach will provide significant insights for academics and the banking sector, allowing for a better understanding of the dynamic interplay between innovation and customer behavior in Kazakh banking.

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